

Prediction of Fuel Consumption in Forest Machines with the Application of Experimentable Digital Twins

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ABSTRACT

Fuel consumption in forest machines is a widely discussed topic in terms of its ecological importance towards climate-neutral wood harvesting operations. Various research has been and is being carried out in this area to understand the forest machine, its movements, and other activities that affect fuel consumption. However, fuel consumption and in turn carbon emissions not only depend on the forest machine itself but rely vastly on the several physical aspects of the forest such as the terrain, soil, forest, and tree parameters. This requires an effective system to predict fuel consumption under the varying physical conditions in the forest. Hence, the prediction of fuel consumption and carbon emission requires detailed simulations that take all relevant machine and environmental parameters into account. This paper provides extensive information on the existing state of the art, and a deep insight into the concept of fuel consumption prediction by laying out a brief note on, data requirements, acquisition, and the simulation design process.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the field of robotics and mechatronics, simulation technologies play an important role in the development and operation of robotic systems. Besides this, Digital Twins are one of the core technologies of Industry 4.0. The Industry 4.0 revolution, specifically in manufacturing, is currently characterized by the widespread usage of digital twin technology. Through technological advancements, it is quickly expanding into new application domains such as Earth's ecosystems [1]. Digital twins are built on a two-way information flow that begins when asset sensors give the system processor pertinent data and continue to provide the data while the processor shares insights with the original source. Developing forestry digital twins in particular is demanding due to the ever-changing physical conditions of the forest environment. The necessity of efficient and carbon-neutral timber management that is based on the accurate prediction of the fuel consumption and CO₂ emission in the forest machines is the starting point of this paper. The principal idea here is to consider the workflow-integrated prediction of

fuel consumption and CO₂ emission at the level of single trees and specific harvesting actions which are missing in recent studies.

2 STATE OF THE ART

2.1 Measuring Fuel Consumption and Calculating CO₂ Emissions

Previous fuel consumption studies have highlighted the significant effects of harvesting conditions (such as stem size, cutting method, and a number of timber assortments), machine properties (such as engine power, type of machine, adjustments, and use of tracks and wheel chains), and machine operators (such as level of education and skills) have a significant effect on the fuel consumption of the harvester as shown in the following studies (References [2] to [10]). In both harvesters and forwarders, it was discovered that engine power and machine hours (i.e., age of the machine unit) had the biggest and most significant effects on hour-based fuel consumption. Cutting technique and air temperature had an impact on harvesters' hourly fuel usage [11]. The harvesting conditions for hectare-based removals, such as the removal stem size in the stand, the manner of felling, the forwarding distance, and the kind of soil, had the biggest impact on both harvesters and forwarders [12]. The above studies show that there are multiple techniques to measure fuel consumption in terms of time, cubic meters, and hectare based. Although the methods are different the environment and the machine parameters involved are the same which leads to the estimation of the consumption.

2.2 Estimation of Fuel Consumption and Simulation of Mechanized Harvesting

Fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions among forest machines are widely studied topics. Various parameters and different methodologies are applied to the calculation of fuel consumption including whether the system is cable yarding or ground-based. Due to the continually shifting topography and stand characteristics, logging operations have an impact on the usage of fuel equipment and harvesting systems [13]. However, the majority of the research in this area is focused only on the economic valuation of timber management but

Figure 1: Left: Petrinets for harvesting operation simulation conducted in Arnsberg, Germany. Right: Rigid Body Simulation of a ground harvester.

not on the prediction of fuel consumption Simulation of harvesting techniques is not a new topic and various simulation approaches have already been developed. [14] provides an overview of discrete event simulation of mechanized wood harvesting system which is one of the early works on the simulation concept for forestry. However, the prior works on the forest simulation concepts were limited by their time and existing computational requirements to realize the technology. [15] claimed that most forestry simulation tools are created to address specific silvicultural issues and regional harvesting issues. As a result, their utility is limited and there are multiple complex parameters that must be considered in the forest environment [16]. Considering these drawbacks, AutoMod simulation software was used for managing the wood supply chain and optimizing timber harvesting where multiple aspects such as forest environment and information from the machines that are deployed were considered to achieve a model that is close to reality [17]. However, it requires more detailed modeling down to every single movement of the machine and individual tree data as shown in Figure 1 which is discussed in depth in section 5, to make reliable predictions of fuel consumption.

3 RESEARCH GAP, HYPOTHESIS AND QUESTIONS

3.1 Research Gap and Hypothesis

The majority of the research that is being conducted on the topic of calculation fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions mostly considers the average values of different parameters such as harvesting operations performed over an area of land, or the fuel consumption statistics collected annually for different machines. Besides, the studies are mostly focused on

the calculation of fuel consumption and not on the concept of prediction. This research will bridge these gaps through system-cohesive prediction of fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions which is hypothesized through the analysis of 1) the physical parameters of the forest including the single tree data (dimensions), the position of the trees, and the digital terrain model of the surface, and 2) the machine data that includes the fuel consumption values acquired by the CAN module, a detailed petri-net and physical simulation can be developed that establishes the digital twins and this is used to formulate the prediction equation for the fuel consumption and later correlate it to the CO₂ emissions.

3.2 Research Questions

What level of detail is required for the forest machine digital twin? This leans towards the type of simulations that must be considered such as (physical) continuous-time vs. (process-oriented) discrete event simulation. One provides an efficient approach to simulate the individual events and actions of the entire process of the harvesting operation, and the other gives a detailed demonstration of the movement made by the harvester.

Which data is required to calibrate and adjust the digital twins of forest machines and forest? There is an abundant amount of information that is available related to the machine and the forest environment where it is deployed such as the machine data (type, movements) and forest data (terrain conditions, slope, soil conditions) that increases the complexity of the system. Therefore, it is important to understand to what extent the available data can be used.

How can fuel consumption be predicted? What simulation results are required for this? Once the simulation scenario is set up and the relevant data is included, it raises

the most important question as to how to model the Digital Twins and predict the fuel consumption and CO2 emissions?

4 REQUIRED AND AVAILABLE DATA

The development of the simulation to predict the fuel consumption of the machine requires data describing the forest environment including data on the terrain and trees (geo-location of the trees, tree height, width, species) as well as machine-related data such as movements or engine parameters. The following data sets and tools are used in the process of this research.

4.1 Digital Terrain Model and Machine Data

The **Digital Terrain Model (DTM)** includes forest data sets such as the slope of the surface, position of the trees, tree dimensions, tree maps, and geolocation of the trees captured by the GPS device. Figure 2 (Left) depicts a DTM designed to

Figure 2: DTM to calculate the slope of the surface (Left). CANBus Data: Harvester Movements (Right)

calculate the slope percentage for the harvesting operations performed in Arnsberg, Germany. The points represent two lines of trees with their geo-location with a mean slope percentage of 29.17.

Machine Data: The CAN module uses a plug-and-play logger to capture timestamped data of the Machine It connects via WLAN or 3G/4G routers or other Wi-Fi access points in order to securely deliver data to the server. This tool is mostly used to gather information about engine parameters, like rpm, fuel usage, and torque, to name a few. The device is connected to the onboard diagnostics of the harvester. The graph in Figure 2 (Right) shows one of the elements that is captured by the CANBus which is the movement of the harvester from one geolocation to the other. However, the standstill state of the machine implies that it is performing harvesting operations. The other elements that are recorded by the CANBus data are the GPS locations of the entire machine, the acceleration rate of the machine, engine speed and torque, and movement of the joysticks to perform actions such as grabbing, felling, and debranching the tree. These movements of the joystick can then be coordinated with the joystick manual of the particular harvester in use to analyze the movement patterns.

5 CONCEPT

In this research, the physical environment of the forest is replicated by its **forest digital twin FDT**, taking into account various details that significantly impact the consumption of fuel in the forest machines including slope conditions, single tree data (tree dimensions), geo-location of the trees, soil conditions (moisture). Within this simulated forest environment and the **TDT (terrain digital twin)**, the **machine digital twin MDT** (harvester, logger, skidder etc..) are in turn simulated based on their activity (Figure 3).

5.1 Experimentable Digital Twins and Forest Digital Twins

The overall digital twin concept has been around for some time now since Dr. Michael Grieves first announced the concept and applied the idea of digital twins to manufacturing two decades ago. The digital twins are created through the object sensors offering relevant data to the system. To achieve this, all possible interactions between the system and the ecosystem where it is deployed must be modeled. This increases the complexity of the model and makes it difficult to ensure its totality. The experimentable digital twins (EDTs) integrate the concepts of digital twins with model-based systems engineering and simulation technology which independently models the different parts of the system that combine to form a complex EDT scenario that is analyzed inside a virtual testbed [18]. Applying this concept to forest

Figure 3: Conceptualization of the Fuel Consumption Prediction.

Figure 4: Components of FDTs and MDTs.

machine measurements and various physical state variables at both the tree and forest levels creates a virtual replica of the forest which forms a forest digital twin (FDT). Figure 4 shows the individual EDTs - FDT, TDT, and MDT forming one complex EDT scenario. The simulations for these EDTs are developed not only to accurately mimic the actions of

the machine that is deployed in the real scenario but also to react to the forest environment conditions. Furthermore, it will also help in the development of a virtual driver that will adapt to the prediction values to efficiently proceed with the harvesting operations.

5.2 3D Timber/Wood Harvesting Simulation

The discrete event simulation (DES) technique will be used to simulate real-world systems that may be broken down into a number of conceptually distinct processes that advance on their own. The result of the harvesting event can be an outcome that is transmitted to one or more additional processes. A petrinet [19] is used to model the individual process steps of the harvesting process. Petrinet is a state graph consisting of *places* that is a specific simulation state, *transitions* which are actions with a duration that will change the simulation state, *arrows* connect the places to transitions, and *marks* are simulation resources. A mark traverses the petrinet. That is, if it enters a transition, actions can be executed such as felling the tree. These actions can also be displayed in the simulation including its maneuver during obstruction and limitations (tree out of reach) as shown in Figure 1 Left. Each transition has a duration that can be combined to compute the duration of the whole operation and in turn, determine fuel consumption. Since the simulation is only event-based, the animation resolution of the model is limited. However, the study of detailed machine movements will result in more accurate predictions.

5.3 Rigid Body Dynamics

The concept presented here will combine petrinets with a physical simulation that integrates single tree data and specific harvesting action to develop a workflow-integrated prediction of fuel consumption. RBD is the most frequent sort of physics simulation. A rigid body object is a solid geometry with either no deformation or deformation that is negligible. Figure 1 Right, shows the working example of RBD simulation where the “felled tree is being grabbed by the harvester head”. The simulation technique uses a highly realistic model to precisely simulate all the physical characteristics of the machines, including torque, force, the motors responsible for movement, and many elements found in an actual vehicle.

5.4 Combination of Petrinets and Rigid Body Simulation

The future goal here is to merge two simulation approaches (Petrinets and RBD). A complex scenario will be represented step-by-step using petrinets in discrete event simulation, and specific actions will be physically simulated in great detail in the continuous simulation (RBD). For instance, the timed

Figure 5: Combination of results from DES and RBD.

events such as the forward movement of the machines can be deployed in discrete event simulation and the detailed machine actions performed by the machine can be designed in rigid body dynamics. This provides the flexibility to maneuver the simulation depending on the requirements and the focus areas that must be taken into account in the prediction of fuel consumption. Figure 5 shows the combination structure divided into three layers. the data and the model layer form the Digital Twin and the simulation layer enables evaluation.

6 FIRST RESULTS AND FUTURE WORK

Preliminary results show the petrinets and corresponding simulation designed for the harvesting action performed in Arnsberg, Germany in November 2022 to establish a skid trail, the simulation of which is shown in Figure 6. The harvester is designed to move strictly in a straight green line as depicted in the images similar to the real scenario by making negligible smaller movements to move around the bushes that block the way. Using this simulation, along with the machine data, not only the fuel consumption is predicted, but it can also be programmed to perform different harvesting scenarios. The next steps in this research are to include the data from the CANBus module that involves the movement of the harvester, speed, distance traveled, and the corresponding fuel consumption. Using these details, the prediction equation will be formulated for fuel consumption and CO2 emission.

6.1 Conclusion and Acknowledgements

This paper introduces digital twins and how they can be implemented in the field of timber management with a focus on the prediction of fuel consumption and in turn CO2 emission. It provides a detailed overview of the current studies that are being conducted on this topic and their limitations, The data required and tools for acquisition are discussed in detail. The paper also provides a brief note on the research questions and the gaps that need to be bridged for the accurate and effective prediction of fuel consumption. Furthermore, it conceptualizes the idea and path of this research with the initial results and next steps.

Figure 6: Simulation of Arnsberg site for the provision of skid trail.

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